

Australian Research Data Commons

Acknowledgement Guidelines 2025/27

The Logo - Master Logo

ARDC Master Logo

The ARDC logo is the primary signifier of the organisation and the brand. Use the standard version of our logo to represent our brand - pictured to the right.

The logo should be used in a clear space, large enough to be seen but not so large that it distracts from the content.

Australian Research Data Commons

The Logo - Clear Space and Minimum Size

Clear Space

The ARDC logo needs to be surrounded by an area of uninterrupted clear space to allow it to remain prominent in all communications. Clear space is the non print area surrounding the logo.

No other graphic elements (such as photography or typography) should appear within this zone. Wherever possible, apply more clear space than the minimum specified.

Minimum Size

To avoid any possible reproduction problems, the logo must never be reproduced at a size smaller than the minimum specified width.

35mm / 200px

The Logo - Incorrect Usage

Incorrect Usage

The examples show here are of changes to our logo that diminish its impact and dilute our brand and are therefore not correct.

X Do not add drop shadows

X Do not distort the proportions

X Do not use on coloured background

X Do not add gradients

X Do not use on a complex background

X Do not alter the opacity or tint

X Do not reconfigure elements

X Do not change colour

X Do not use on an angle

ARDC / NCRIS Relationship

In line with the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) acknowledgement guidelines, all partners in ARDC co-investment projects are required to acknowledge the ARDC co-investment partnership with ARDC and NCRIS logos together with standard text on websites, presentations and promotional materials about the project. Logo variations including reverse and monochromatic are available on request.

There are 2 ways to show NCRIS support in conjunction with the ARDC logo. Please ask the ARDC Communications team for guidance

1 - Together with the combined NCRIS and Australian Government logo

The logos should be separated by 1.5x clear space.

2 - Together with the NCRIS logo (An Australian Government Initiative)

The logos should be separated by 1.5x clear space.

For assistance, and approval of ARDC and NCRIS logo use, please contact comms@ardc.edu.au.

1 - Together with the combined NCRIS and Australian Government logo

2 - Together with the NCRIS logo (An Australian Government Initiative)

Acknowledgement Text

The acknowledgement detailed on this page must be included in all co-branding arrangements. It should specify the name of the service or project, the Research Data Commons with which it is associated (Planet, People or HASS and Indigenous) if relevant, and the project DOI.

For assistance, and approval of ARDC and NCRIS logo use, please contact comms@ardc.edu.au.

Co-investment through the ARDC Thematic Research Data Commons initiatives:

[Project name] is a co-investment partnership with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) through the [Planet/People/HASS and Indigenous] Research Data Commons (DOI: [insert project DOI hyperlinked to DOI URL]). The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

Co-investment through other ARDC initiatives:

[Project name] is a co-investment partnership with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) (DOI: [insert project DOI hyperlinked to DOI URL]). The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

Acknowledging services supported through a co-investment partnership:

[Service name] is supported through a co-investment partnership with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) [through the Planet/People/HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons] (DOI: [insert project DOI hyperlinked to DOI URL]). The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

Example of a co-investment partnership acknowledgement

The Language Data Commons of Australia is supported through a co-investment partnership with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) through the HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons (DOI: [10.3565/kq2v-9g52](https://doi.org/10.3565/kq2v-9g52)). The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

The Logo - Co-branding

ARDC / NCRIS Co-branding

Horizontal

ARDC partners and collaborators should use their own Brand Guidelines for material that they produce and use their judgement on how to apply the co-branding information provided in this document.

ARDC

When partnering with ARDC, use these simple guidelines for the best visual balance:

- When sizing logos, try to match the text or cap heights.
- Use a double X clear space between partnering logo and the ARDC logo.
- Use the ARDC clear space to determine the distances of each element in the co-branding lock-up.

NCRIS

The NCRIS logo should be placed in a secondary position and must be proportional to the size of any adjacent logos.

Arrangements

Co-branding arrangements can be placed above, below or between the ARDC and NCRIS logos.

For assistance, and approval of ARDC and NCRIS logo use, please contact comms@ardc.edu.au.

Acknowledgement with combined NCRIS and Australian Government logo

The Logo - Co-branding

ARDC / NCRIS Co-branding

Horizontal

ARDC partners and collaborators should use their own Brand Guidelines for material that they produce and use their judgement on how to apply the co-branding information provided in this document.

ARDC

When partnering with ARDC, use these simple guidelines for the best visual balance:

- When sizing logos, try to match the text or cap heights.
- Use a double X clear space between partnering logo and the ARDC logo.
- Use the ARDC clear space to determine the distances of each element in the co-branding lock-up.

NCRIS

The NCRIS logo should be placed in a secondary position and must be proportional to the size of any adjacent logos.

Arrangements

Co-branding arrangements can be placed above, below or between the ARDC and NCRIS logos.

For assistance, and approval of ARDC and NCRIS logo use, please contact comms@ardc.edu.au.

Acknowledgement with NCRIS logo (An Australian Government Initiative)

The Logo - Co-branding

ARDC / NCRIS Co-branding

Vertical

The vertical lock-up can be used for portrait layouts such as posters, brochures and reports.

This acknowledgement example is for when vertical space is limited and the arrangement is constructed in a compact horizontal format.

Arrangements

Partner logos may appear elsewhere in the layout to adhere to its own brand guidelines but on occasions where the communication requires co-branding, all the logos will appear in as shown in the example vertical lock-up.

Partner / ARDC / NCRIS / Acknowledgement

When partnering with ARDC, use these simple guidelines for the best visual balance:

- Align both the ARDC and NCRIS logos, including the acknowledgement text to the left.
- If a partner logo appears elsewhere, and not as illustrated in this example, then the ARDC/NCRIS lock-up can stand alone and positioned to suit the layout.
- The acknowledgement text needs to span the width of the vertical arrangement.
- ARDC clear space is used throughout the structure of this arrangement.

For assistance, and approval of ARDC and NCRIS logo use, please contact comms@ardc.edu.au.

Acknowledgement with combined NCRIS and Australian Government logo

Example showing acknowledgement of a co-investment partnership

LDaCA

A R D C

Australian Research Data Commons

Australian Government

NCRIS
National Research
Infrastructure for Australia

The Language Data Commons of Australia is supported through a co-investment partnership with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) through the HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons (DOI: [10.35665/kq2v-9g52](https://doi.org/10.35665/kq2v-9g52)). The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

The Logo - Co-branding

ARDC / NCRIS Co-branding

Vertical

The vertical lock-up can be used for portrait layouts such as posters, brochures and reports.

This acknowledgement example is for when vertical space is limited and the arrangement is constructed in a compact horizontal format.

Arrangements

Partner logos may appear elsewhere in the layout to adhere to its own brand guidelines but on occasions where the communication requires co-branding, all the logos will appear in as shown in the example vertical lock-up.

Partner / ARDC / NCRIS / Acknowledgement

When partnering with ARDC, use these simple guidelines for the best visual balance:

- Align both the ARDC and NCRIS logos, including the acknowledgement text to the left.
- If a partner logo appears elsewhere, and not as illustrated in this example, then the ARDC/NCRIS lock-up can stand alone and positioned to suit the layout.
- The acknowledgement text needs to span the width of the vertical arrangement.
- ARDC clear space is used throughout the structure of this arrangement.

For assistance, and approval of ARDC and NCRIS logo use, please contact comms@ardc.edu.au.

Acknowledgement with NCRIS logo (An Australian Government Initiative)

Example showing acknowledgement of a co-investment partnership

LDaCA

Australian Research Data Commons

The Language Data Commons of Australia is supported through a co-investment partnership with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) through the HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons (DOI: 10.3565/kq2v-9g52). The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

The Logo - Partnerships

ARDC Partnerships

When ARDC partners with other companies and organisations, such as CSIRO, AuScope or Pawsey, the ARDC master logo should be used.

The size of the logo in relation to the other partners will largely depend on the importance of the relationship but where possible should be of equal weighting.

Partnered With 1 Logo

Use a dividing line between the 2 logos to maintain visual distinction and the clear space rules to place logos at optimum distance.

Partnered With Multiple Logos

Use 1.5x clear space rule to place logos at optimum distance.

For assistance, and approval of ARDC and NCRIS logo use, please contact comms@ardc.edu.au.

Partnered With One Logo

Partnered With Partnered With Multiple Logos

Australian Research Data Commons

HEAD OFFICE

Monash University, Ground Floor, Building T,
900 Dandenong Road, Caulfield East, VIC 3145

FOLLOW

- [australian-research-data-commons](https://www.linkedin.com/company/australian-research-data-commons)
- [ARDC_AU](https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCARDC_AU)
- Subscribe to the ARDC Connect Newsletter
<https://ardc.edu.au/subscribe/>

CONTACT

- ardc.edu.au
- +61 3 9902 0585
- contact@ardc.edu.au